

Establishing a Central Helpdesk for KonsortSWD - NFDI4Society: Goals, Challenges, and Solutions

Robert Herrenbrück¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6851-1590>

¹ DIPF | Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

Abstract

Over the past decades, a wide range of research data centers (RDCs) have been established in Germany and are closely connected under the Umbrella of RatSWD and now of KonsortSWD - NFDI4Society. The scope and complexity of this service infrastructure have further increased since the establishment of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). There are now more than 40 RDCs with a wide range of services in KonsortSWD[1]. This diversity makes it increasingly difficult for researchers to navigate the structures and find appropriate offers. This is especially true for researchers who have not yet had much contact with KonsortSWD.

To address this issues, KonsortSWD established a central contact point for inquiries : the KonsortSWD Helpdesk. On the KonsortSWD website, users can submit their questions on various topics using a contact form. These questions are processed in a ticket system. General questions are answered directly, while specific questions are forwarded to the most appropriate contact points within KonsortSWD or even to other NFDI Helpdesks[2]. When responsibilities are unclear, the Helpdesk also coordinates the exchange between institutions to ensure that inquiries are properly assigned. Additionally, the Helpdesk is designed to evolve iteratively with regular evaluations of key performance indicators to inform ongoing improvements.

The current structure is the result of several challenges encountered during the establishment phase of the Helpdesk. A major challenge was ensuring that it complements rather than duplicates existing advisory structures. Many RDCs already operate established contact points for specific services. Furthermore, advisory staff should not have to work within multiple overlapping structures. To address this, the Helpdesk was designed as a signposting system in which specific inquiries are forwarded to appropriate RDCs. This ensures that researchers receive the support they need efficiently while allowing popular services to continue operating within their established structures.

To support efficient forwarding of inquiries and strengthen internal knowledge about the services of other RDCs, a knowledge database was set up and is currently being expanded. The technical basis for this is Forum4MICA, one of KonsortSWD's already established advisory services.

Another major challenge is data protection. Forwarding inquiries between institutions involves the transfer of personal data, which requires careful legal consideration. To ensure transparency, users are informed from the outset that their inquiries may be forwarded, and a legal framework for joint responsibility in data protection is being established within KonsortSWD.

This session provides insights into the development and operational processes of the Helpdesk, discussing key challenges, solutions, and lessons learned. Additionally, we will present initial usage data, including the main topics researchers have inquired about. By improving access to research data services while respecting existing advisory structures, the

Helpdesk serves as a key interface connecting researchers with the diverse expertise across KonsortSWD.

Keywords: Educating RDM, Helpdesk, Service Infrastructure, Knowledge Management, Social Science, Research Data Centers (RDCs), Inter-institutional Coordination

Resources

The contact form of the Helpdesk can be found here: <https://www.konsortswd.de/en/services/research/support/konsortswd-helpdesk/>

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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